

Harnessing the global urban microbiome for the future of cities

Authors

Alexander G. Lucaci¹, Bethlehem Judah², Oona Shigeno Risse-Adams¹, Eyup Alper Saygili¹, Xavier Rodó³, The International MetaSUB Consortium, Haruo Suzuki⁴, Eran Elhaik⁵, Christopher E. Mason¹

Affiliations

1. Department of Systems and Computational Biomedicine, Weill Cornell Medicine, New York, NY, USA, 10065
2. Oakland University William Beaumont School of Medicine, Rochester, MI, USA, 48309
3. ICREA and Climate and Health RG, CANU, ISGlobal, Barcelona, Spain 08003
4. Faculty of Environment and Information Studies, Keio University, Fujisawa, Kanagawa, 252-0882, Japan
5. Lund University, Department of Biology, Lund, Sweden, 22362

Correspondance: agl4001@med.cornell.edu, chm2042@med.cornell.edu

Abstract

Cities are as biological as they are architectural. Beyond the surface of each city lies an infrastructure of urban microbes and biology which play key roles in our health and development. However, these microbial ecosystems remain largely invisible to urban planners, designers, and public health teams. Rapid environmental DNA sequencing now enables us to monitor the microbial (and eukaryotic) life of cities in near real time, transforming our understanding of urban ecology and evolutionary dynamics, while providing novel tools for public health. Projects such as MetaSUB have revealed that each city possesses a distinct microbial fingerprint, with measurable implications for outbreak detection, infection control, and disease risk. Despite the insights gained to date, major gaps persist including inconsistent sampling methods across studies, geographic disparities, and a divide between environmental and clinical microbiology. Bridging these gaps requires a significant reframing of microbial life as a core asset of urban infrastructure in city design, healthcare systems, and sustainability initiatives. We outline a roadmap for building microbiome-informed cities, emphasizing routine microbial surveillance, clinical integration, while advancing microbial literacy among city planners, health professionals, and urban residents. Cities of the future will be judged not only by factors such as their air and water quality, but also by the sustainability of their urban microbiomes and by our ability to harness them to design healthy urban landscapes for both the microscopic and macroscopic residents.

Main

Every city has microbiomes, yet few urban residents are aware of them¹⁻⁵. Microbes circulate through buses and subway cars, coat the surfaces of hospitals and schools, and drift in the aerosols across office corridors⁶⁻⁸. When it rains, these microbes filter through the water and soil systems beneath the pavement^{1,2,9-12}. Not only are these microbes a part of the urban infrastructure, such as the buildings, highways, sewers, and public transit, but they also outnumber the city's human population and their associated microbiomes by several orders of magnitude. However, unlike other urban assets, they remain largely invisible. This level of invisibility persists, despite a growing recognition that microbes not only influence individual health (e.g., through the gut microbiome and sewage), but also the evolution, health, and sustainability of entire populations^{8,13-17}.

Microbial exposures are mostly not incidental, but instead cumulative, and these exposures shape immune responses, antimicrobial resistance (AMR) risks, and ultimately clinical presentations of infections¹⁸⁻²⁰. Prolonged periods of reduced exposure, particularly for children raised during the height of the pandemic, may alter immune development²¹. This phenomenon is best understood through the lens of the 'Old Friends' or "Hygiene" hypotheses, which posit that the human immune system requires constant calibration by commensal microbes, organisms we co-evolved with in natural environments, to develop regulatory T-cell function and distinguish harmless antigens from pathogens²². Sterilization of the urban sphere removes these necessary microbial developmental inputs, potentially replacing the risk of infectious disease with the risk of chronic inflammatory and autoimmune disorders. Thus, the goal of the future city should not be sterility, which creates an immunological void, but rather a managed microbial balance that suppresses pathogens while preserving the biodiverse exposures essential for human health and proper immune system development. While the urban microbiome is a dynamic ecosystem of microbial communities, it is not a random assortment; a city's biome reflects the geography, climate, architecture, history, and social behavior.

Diverse microbial communities in urban environments consist of pathogens, commensals, and beneficial species that regulate immunity, cycle nutrients, and degrade pollutants in our environment (e.g. Gowanus Canal, Brooklyn, New York)²³. In this sense, the urban microbiome is both a mirror of human activity and an evolutionary ecosystem in its own right. Recent advances from molecular sampling techniques, high-throughput sequencing (HTS), portable sequencing technology, data storage, and computational analysis allow mapping microbial dynamics at an unprecedented scale²⁴. As demonstrated and accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, extensive wastewater genomic surveillance (WWGS) can yield population-level insights faster than clinical testing alone²⁵⁻²⁸. As cities expand, local microbial monitoring could inform empirical data-based prescribing practices for antibiotics and other medicines. Microbial communities cycle at daily, weekly, seasonally, and interannual paces/scales, depending on cities geographic location, altitude, distance to the sea, and regional climate. Meanwhile, growing antimicrobial resistance, climate-driven ecological change, and rapid global urbanization highlight the urgency of understanding how microbes shape life in cities⁵. This perspective argues that microbes must be recognized as a part of the urban infrastructure, and appropriately monitored and engineered. Just as cities monitor air quality, energy flows, and

water safety, they should also monitor their microbiomes to inform baselines, dynamics, and potential health risks. Baselines represent the normal operating range of a city over a period and include expected ratios, composition, diversity, and AMR patterns under ordinary conditions. Establishing an urban microbial baseline enables the detection of deviations, the quantification of their magnitude, and the interpretation of their underlying causes, and can even be a source of new biotechnology (e.g. CRISPR systems).

We argue that the failure to treat microbial life as urban infrastructure represents a structural blind spot in modern city design and public health. Unlike air, water, or energy systems, microbial ecosystems are neither routinely measured nor governed, despite shaping antimicrobial resistance, outbreak dynamics, and long-term immune health. This omission is no longer tenable. We view the microbiome as an integral part of the city's infrastructure and offer a forward-looking perspective on how to sustain it.

Insights from the microbial signatures of cities

Research over the past decade has shown that urban environments harbor distinct microbial signatures that can be measured, compared, and in some cases used as predictors of community-level health^{3,29,29–34}. These insights, while still partial, form the foundation for thinking about how cities might integrate microbial signatures into practice. Published work thus far has already yielded actionable insights for outbreak detection, antimicrobial resistance monitoring, roles of the urban green and blue spaces, and understanding toxic environmental exposures^{35,36}. The evidence gained to date demonstrates a key point: that urban microbiomes are consequential, measurable, and inseparable from the health of the populations that live within them.

Mapping the microbiome of urban transit systems.

The MetaSUB consortium, a global initiative to map the microbiome of urban transit systems, has demonstrated that cities possess unique microbial fingerprints and “molecular echoes”^{37,38}. Transit system studies consistently reveal a mix of environmental microbes, commensal human-associated taxa, and occasional pathogens^{6,39}. As environments where hundreds of millions of people converge daily, transit systems serve as dynamic microbial hubs with “microbial fingerprints” unique to each city and can even characterize districts within cities^{40,41}. Samples collected from transit systems in global cities show consistent region-specific microbial profiles (AMR dynamics and microbial ‘core’ species constituents)³⁸, despite having shared generalized modes of urban human behavior (high-density, public transit systems) and global connectivity. While they are alike in that they are molded by human activity, each city also has patterns in respective microbial “hotspots” which are shaped by factors in the local environment, including climate, fauna, and existing urban design^{42,43} (Figure 1) This correlates with population density, geography, and existing ecological structures. Microbial signatures cannot only differentiate cities but also provide baselines (characteristic microbial profiles) against which future changes can be measured.

Wastewater as a public health lens

Perhaps the most striking insight into the urban microbiome has come from leveraging data in WWGS^{25,25-28}. During the COVID-19 pandemic, SARS-CoV-2 RNA was detected in community wastewater before increases in clinical case counts⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸. WWGS captures both symptomatic and asymptomatic cases and offers an early warning system for emerging pathogens and their variants⁴⁸. WWGS has proven that environmental microbial sequencing can provide near-real-time population-scale health surveillance. Beyond viruses, wastewater microbiome studies have revealed patterns of AMR gene prevalence in cities globally and have also detected nutritional biomarkers and even indicators of community-level health behaviors⁴². This body of research demonstrates that the sewer system is not merely a sanitation endpoint, but rather it offers a rich lens into the urban population's collective health.

Built environments as microbial hubs

Buildings are microbial ecosystems of their own⁴. Humans continually imprint these environments with their host microbiota and simultaneously receive microbial inputs back, forming a constant bidirectional flow between people and the built environment⁴⁹⁻⁵¹. Studies of subways, hospitals, schools, and office buildings have shown that the built environment acts as microbial hubs where human contact, ventilation, and surface materials converge^{52,53}. Hospitals, by contrast, often act as amplifiers of pathogenic organisms, with hospital-acquired infections representing both a breakdown of infection control and a reflection of the surrounding city microbiome. The boundary between community and hospital microbiomes is permeable, with pathogens circulating and being interchanged in both directions. Building design choices, however, such as ventilation and water systems, construction materials, and the incorporation of blue (water) and green (plants) spaces, also shape microbial exposures and directly impact occupants. Collectively, these findings underscore that the built environment is simultaneously molded by, and actively molds, the urban microbiome, making it a measurable and dynamic reference system for defining urban microbial baselines.

Clinical and public health connections

A growing body of evidence demonstrates that the urban microbiome is not just a passive ecological environment, but is directly relevant to human health^{3,29-33,33,34}. Airborne microbial communities influence rates of asthma and allergies: microbial exposure in childhood can train immunity, while its absence may predispose individuals to inflammatory disease²⁹. Such exposures are not incidental but cumulative, ultimately shaping clinical presentations. Hospital and wastewater microbiome studies may anticipate and inform infection control strategies, offering data that complements clinical diagnostics. For physicians, understanding the microbial activity inside a hospital, where sick patients concentrate together with clinicians becomes paramount to safeguarding public health inside hospitals, as well as preventing expansion of pathogenic strains out of hospital settings. Complementary, city microbiome exposures may one day also be as important as knowing a patient's occupation or travel history. These insights lead us to a vision for the future where aggregated environmental data informs both public health policy and bedside clinical decision-making.

Urban microbiology must address its knowledge gaps with comprehensive sampling and analysis.

Although studies of the urban microbiome have already delivered important insights, the field is still in its infancy⁵⁴⁻⁵⁷. Current data sets resemble scattered snapshots rather than comprehensive maps of urban environments, and much of what we know is biased towards a few well-studied cities or countries, partially due to publication bias in the microbiome field (Figure 3). To move from proof of concept studies to the assembly of key insights into actionable public health and urban planning advice, critical gaps must be addressed in several areas, including: data sampling, longitudinal studies beyond point-analysis, data storage and access, metadata curation, molecular and computational methods, equity, and governance. The urban microbiome research field has revealed the contours of a new and consequential domain of city life but the maps are incomplete. Without longitudinal microbial baselines, global inclusivity, clinical integration, and ethical governance, the promise of studying the urban microbiome will remain unrealized. The challenge now is to move from fragmented studies to comprehensive systems that link microbial ecology and evolution to health outcomes.

Data and methodological gaps

Most urban microbiome studies are, by design, cross-sectional projects that capture microbial diversity at a single (or limited) time point. This interferes with our ability to understand important temporal dynamics, especially how communities shift seasonally, respond to extreme weather, or change in response to new infrastructure being built. In addition, studies often use different sampling protocols (ignoring daily cycles of microbes), sequencing depths, and apply bioinformatics pipelines without standardization and harmonization, making direct comparisons between studies difficult. Without longitudinal datasets and methodological standardization, it is nearly impossible to distinguish natural variation from meaningful ecological or clinical signals. Additionally, this creates the risk of a growing microbial divide, in which the best resource cities benefit while others are left with data blind spots. A balanced and comprehensive approach is essential to ensure that the urban microbiome is a global science and not just a feature of select megacities or small teams.

Emerging sequencing technologies, and their associated price reduction, now enable the observation of the urban microbiome with unprecedented depth and resolution. Beyond classical metagenomics analysis (the workhorse of the field), metatranscriptomics captures real-time functional activity of RNAs, revealing actively replicating viruses, pathogens, and AMR expression. Long-read sequencing resolves complete genomes, mobile elements, and strain dynamics, prophage integration sites, while Hi-C-enabled metagenomics links plasmids, phages, and AMR genes to their hosts. Single-cell metagenomics recovers genomes from rare or unculturable taxa, overcoming assembly barriers and exposing otherwise invisible components of indoor and outdoor ecosystems. Together, these complementary modalities, when integrated through emerging computational frameworks, create the foundation for assembling truly multimodal urban microbiome datasets.

Clinical and environmental disconnects

Clinical microbiology and environmental metagenomics are often treated as separate domains. However, in reality, they are deeply intertwined. Hospitals are not isolated microbial environments, but concentrated extensions of the surrounding city⁵⁸. Resistant organisms circulate between communities and clinics, and exposures in schools or transit systems may drive the infections that clinicians confront in emergency rooms by failing to connect clinical and environmental data sets⁵⁹. This means missing opportunities to anticipate outbreaks (including seasonal outbreaks), refine prescribing practices for AMR, and design interventions that span both healthcare and the built environment. In the future, we may move towards patients having a “precision microbiome” approach, which generates actionable, context-specific insights into microbial communities at the strain and functional levels, benefiting from knowledge gained from understanding the urban environment in which they live⁶⁰. Bridging the gap between medical practice and environmental science is essential, and such a framework enables physicians to translate microbial ecology into actionable insights for patient care. By improving medical training to include literacy in environmental microbiology and metagenomic surveillance, future physicians can be better equipped to interpret environmental data as readily as laboratory values or imaging studies. Without this shift, students risk being prepared for a clinical sphere that no longer reflects the environments their patients inhabit.

Even as technical challenges persist, the social and ethical dimensions of the urban microbiome remain unresolved. Environmental sequencing frequently captures fragments of human DNA, raising privacy concerns⁶¹. The questions of data ownership, who controls and benefits from city-level microbiome data, have not been adequately addressed. At the same time, microbial risks are not evenly distributed; economically disadvantaged neighborhoods often face disproportionate exposure to hazards such as AMR reservoirs or inadequate sanitation⁶². While having less access to green spaces that provide beneficial microbial diversity. If left unaddressed, these inequities could continue to amplify health disparities rather than reduce them.

Cities in the post-COVID era and beyond

The COVID-19 pandemic, also due to the recognized airborne nature of SARS-CoV-2 virus, was a transformative period during which cities became testing grounds for large-scale microbial surveillance^{44–48,63,64}, and in the US, led to the creation of the National Wastewater Surveillance System (NWSS) During this period, WWGS demonstrated extensively that environmental sequencing was able to detect COVID viral variants (and other pathogens) in circulation in the days or weeks before clinical cases were reported⁶⁴. This validated urban metagenomics as a population-level health tool. This period also established a proof of concept that microbial signals can provide an early warning system for human health and pathogen detection from outbreaks that inform public health interventions. Intensive disinfection, masking, and reduced human mobility significantly altered the patterns of microbial exchange in built environments, while prolonged indoor confinement decreased exposure to environmental and commensal microbes. These are significant shifts that may have downstream effects on the immune development and susceptibility to infection in humans, particularly in young children and

children born during this period. Beyond the immediate impact, COVID-19 exposed both the potential and the limits of microbial surveillance. Cities with established environmental surveillance capacity responded faster to emerging variants, but privacy, data-sharing, and equity concerns constrained implementation. Moving forward, the significant challenge is to sustain WWGS and related programs beyond crisis response and to embed microbial monitoring systems into routine urban public health services, like water testing, while linking them to clinical and environmental data streams⁶³.

A roadmap for designing microbiome-informed cities.

Health and safety: from surveillance to clinical integration

For clinicians and public health agencies, such urban microbiome baselines and seasonal dynamics provide contextual information on patient exposures. An increase in AMR genes in wastewater, for instance, could trigger alerts for hospitals to adjust infection control protocols or empirical antibiotic choices. In this framework, microbial maps become a shared resource for both city planners and healthcare providers. Wastewater metagenomics has already shown that community health signals can be captured before they appear in clinical settings⁶⁵. By extending this approach across schools, transit hubs, and hospitals, we could create early warning systems for outbreaks and highlight elevated/reduced risks, which is especially important for elderly, at-risk, or immunocompromised patients. It could also reach district-level microbial mapping in cities, thereby capable of uncovering what city managers should be paying most attention to due to some areas changing or showing dangerous microbiome fingerprints. Clinicians could use this data to anticipate case surges, adjust testing strategies, or interpret unexplained clusters of illness. In parallel, public health departments could coordinate interventions with hospital networks creating a feedback loop between environmental surveillance and clinical care.

Sustainability, climate, and clinical outcomes

Microbial communities are not only environmental sentinels but also determinants of chronic disease risk⁶⁶⁻⁷⁰. Climate-driven disruptions, such as heat waves, flooding, and changes in air quality, but also characteristic diurnal cycles related to urban metabolism, reshape these microbial exposures, with direct consequences for clinical cases in emergency and pediatric medicine. By integrating comprehensive urban microbiome data into predictive models of respiratory disease or seasonal infection patterns, these models could help clinicians and epidemiologists prepare for and adapt to these shifts. However, microbial risks and benefits are distributed unevenly⁶², where lower socioeconomic neighborhoods often face higher exposure to resistant organisms or contaminated water, while having less access to the green spaces that provide beneficial microbial diversity⁶². For clinicians, this translates into environmental determinants of health that shape patient outcomes and which should be integrated with traditional, individual risk factors.

A roadmap for the future of cities

The advancement of urban microbiome science requires significant coordinated effort with longitudinal and clinically integrated approaches. In the future, the goal should be to establish a

microbial monitoring system in urban environments as a standard component of public health and infrastructure. We propose a roadmap with the following goals:

- ***Short term.*** The short-term goal is to conduct additional microbiome surveys and implement standardized microbial surveillance datasets across wastewater, transit systems, hospitals, airports, and air environments to generate temporal and spatial microbial maps of cities (i.e., baselines). Pairing microbial data analysis with existing public health metrics from epidemiology data will demonstrate direct translational value.
- ***Medium term.*** The medium-term goals should be to integrate microbial datasets into clinical and urban information systems by developing automated pipelines, and dashboards for data sharing between public health departments and healthcare facilities. This will allow them to use microbial indicators to inform infection and antimicrobial control, and environmental design actions.
- ***Long term.*** Our long-term goal is to develop predictive models that integrate microbial, climate, transportation, and demographic data for real-time risk forecasting and continual discovery from the data. Ensuring implementation across global regions and embedding this system into governance will enable evidence-based responses to emerging microbial threats in urban environments.

The challenge is to translate urban microbiome insights into actions. Cities of the future must not only map and monitor microbial life, but also design policies and health systems that leverage this knowledge, and the many opportunities span infrastructure, clinical care, and sustainability. These are all domains that are typically siloed but are deeply interconnected through microbial processes. By integrating urban microbial analytics into both city planning and clinical practice, we can build urban environments that are not only more resilient but also healthier and more equitable for their inhabitants.

The future of urban microbiome studies

The urban microbiome studies conducted to date, spanning subways, hospitals, wastewater, and public spaces, have shown that the urban microbiome is an integral part of the urban infrastructure that shapes health and disease³⁻⁵. We argue that the urban microbiome is a civic asset to be understood, managed, and integrated into urban planning. Measures taken during the COVID-19 pandemic are a prime example of this philosophy; it altered not only how medicine is practiced but also how city residents perceive the microbial risk⁷¹. Subway cars filled with masked and gloved commuters reflected a renewed association of microbes with danger, amplifying forms of mysophobia in urban life.

As microbial shifts unfold, clinicians must be prepared not only to treat disease but also to contextualize the urban microbiome as a ubiquitous and integral component of everyday life. More recently, hospitals have reinstated mask policies in response to virulent H3N2 influenza strains, underscoring the enduring relevance of lessons learned during the COVID-19 pandemic and the need to sustain and expand surveillance and preparedness efforts. Recognizing microbes as infrastructure means bridging several domains that are often siloed. This includes microbiology, clinical medicine, public health, architecture, and city governance. AI-based methods will also serve an important role in the automatic recognition of evolving pathogenic

threats while built into systems that continuously analyze patterns in near-real-time data. This means developing microbial baselines for each city and embedding microbial surveillance into health care systems, and ensuring that microbial benefits are distributed equitably across neighborhoods, states, and nations. Perhaps most importantly, it requires cultivating microbiome literacy so that clinicians, urban planners, and the public alike understand the microbial environment of daily life around them. The future of cities informed by their urban microbiome is not without obstacles, but the cost of inaction is greater. In our age of accelerating urbanization (up to 68% of people in cities by 2050), climate change, and antimicrobial resistance, cities that choose to study their microbiome will be better prepared to safeguard their populations and learn the most from the data.

Acknowledgements

We thank all members of the MetaSUB Consortium for their contributions to sample collection, processing, data generation, and collaborative discussion. We are grateful to the numerous local teams worldwide whose cooperation made this work possible.

Funding support was provided by a combination of institutional funds, philanthropic support, and research grants awarded to members of the MetaSUB Consortium.

Conflicts

C.E.M. is a co-founder of Biotia and the GeoSeeq Foundation.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing financial or non-financial interests.

References

1. Charlop-Powers, Z. *et al.* Urban park soil microbiomes are a rich reservoir of natural product biosynthetic diversity. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **113**, 14811–14816 (2016).
2. Delgado-Baquerizo, M. *et al.* Global homogenization of the structure and function in the soil microbiome of urban greenspaces. *Sci. Adv.* **7**, eabg5809 (2021).
3. Franchitti, E., Caredda, C., Anedda, E. & Traversi, D. Urban Aerobiome and Effects on Human Health: A Systematic Review and Missing Evidence. *Atmosphere* **13**, 1148 (2022).
4. King, G. M. Urban microbiomes and urban ecology: How do microbes in the built environment affect human sustainability in cities? *J. Microbiol.* **52**, 721–728 (2014).
5. Salazar, C. *et al.* Human microbiota drives hospital-associated antimicrobial resistance dissemination in the urban environment and mirrors patient case rates. *Microbiome* **10**, 208 (2022).
6. Hsu, T. *et al.* Urban Transit System Microbial Communities Differ by Surface Type and Interaction with Humans and the Environment. *mSystems* **1**, 10.1128/msystems.00018-16 (2016).
7. Oduaran, O. H. *et al.* Gut microbiome profiling of a rural and urban South African cohort reveals biomarkers of a population in lifestyle transition. *BMC Microbiol.* **20**, 330 (2020).
8. van der Vossen, E. W. J. *et al.* Gut microbiome transitions across generations in different ethnicities in an urban setting—the HELIUS study. *Microbiome* **11**, 99 (2023).
9. Bray, N. & Wickings, K. The Roles of Invertebrates in the Urban Soil Microbiome. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **7**, (2019).
10. Grierson, J., Flies, E. J., Bissett, A., Ammitzboll, H. & Jones, P. Which soil microbiome? Bacteria, fungi, and protozoa communities show different relationships with urban green space type and use-intensity. *Sci. Total Environ.* **863**, 160468 (2023).
11. Peng, Q. *et al.* The effect of developmental stages on microbiome assembly in the phyllosphere and rhizosphere of rice grown in urban area soil. *Environ. Microbiome* **20**, 86 (2025).
12. Schröder, A., Schloter, M., Roccotiello, E., Weisser, W. W. & Schulz, S. Improving ecosystem services of urban soils – how to manage the microbiome of Technosols? *Front. Environ. Sci.* **12**, (2024).

13. Avellán-Llaguno, R. D. *et al.* Composition, Antibiotic Resistance, and Functionality of the Gut Microbiome in Urban Cats. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* **59**, 17258–17274 (2025).
14. Burkhart Colorado, A. S. *et al.* Differential effects of antiretroviral treatment on immunity and gut microbiome composition in people living with HIV in rural versus urban Zimbabwe. *Microbiome* **12**, 18 (2024).
15. Yan, S., Zhang, Y., Huang, J., Liu, Y. & Li, S. Comparative Study of Gut Microbiome in Urban and Rural Eurasian Tree Sparrows. *Animals* **14**, 3497 (2024).
16. Stražar, M. *et al.* Gut microbiome-mediated metabolism effects on immunity in rural and urban African populations. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 4845 (2021).
17. Rosas-Plaza, S. *et al.* Human Gut Microbiome Across Different Lifestyles: From Hunter-Gatherers to Urban Populations. *Front. Microbiol.* **13**, (2022).
18. Cocker, D. *et al.* Healthcare as a driver, reservoir and amplifier of antimicrobial resistance: opportunities for interventions. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **22**, 636–649 (2024).
19. Konopka, J. K., Chatterjee, P., LaMontagne, C. & Brown, J. Environmental impacts of mass drug administration programs: exposures, risks, and mitigation of antimicrobial resistance. *Infect. Dis. Poverty* **11**, 78 (2022).
20. Singh, S. *et al.* Holistic One Health Surveillance Framework: Synergizing Environmental, Animal, and Human Determinants for Enhanced Infectious Disease Management. *ACS Infect. Dis.* **10**, 808–826 (2024).
21. Morales, J. S. *et al.* The Exposome and Immune Health in Times of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Nutrients* **14**, 24 (2022).
22. Rook, G. A. W. The old friends hypothesis: evolution, immunoregulation and essential microbial inputs. *Front. Allergy* **4**, (2023).
23. Kolokotronis, S.-O. *et al.* Metagenomic interrogation of urban Superfund site reveals antimicrobial resistance reservoir and bioremediation potential. *J. Appl. Microbiol.* **136**, lxaf076 (2025).
24. Karasikov, M. *et al.* Efficient and accurate search in petabase-scale sequence repositories. *Nature* **647**, 1036–1044 (2025).

25. Kodera, S. M. *et al.* Microbiome response in an urban river system is dominated by seasonality over wastewater treatment upgrades. *Environ. Microbiome* **18**, 10 (2023).
26. Morin, L. *et al.* Colonization kinetics and implantation follow-up of the sewage microbiome in an urban wastewater treatment plant. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 11634 (2020).
27. Lira, F., Vaz-Moreira, I., Tamames, J., Manaia, C. M. & Martínez, J. L. Metagenomic analysis of an urban resistome before and after wastewater treatment. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 8174 (2020).
28. LaMartina, E. L., Mohaimani, A. A. & Newton, R. J. Urban wastewater bacterial communities assemble into seasonal steady states. *Microbiome* **9**, 116 (2021).
29. Zuo, T., Kamm, M. A., Colombel, J.-F. & Ng, S. C. Urbanization and the gut microbiota in health and inflammatory bowel disease. *Nat. Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* **15**, 440–452 (2018).
30. Mills, J. G. *et al.* Relating Urban Biodiversity to Human Health With the ‘Holobiont’ Concept. *Front. Microbiol.* **10**, (2019).
31. Robinson, J. M. *et al.* Vertical Stratification in Urban Green Space Aerobiomes. *Environ. Health Perspect.* **128**, 117008 (2020).
32. Robinson, J. M., Breed, M. F. & Beckett, R. Probiotic Cities: microbiome-integrated design for healthy urban ecosystems. *Trends Biotechnol.* **42**, 942–945 (2024).
33. Sugden, S., Sanderson, D., Ford, K., Stein, L. Y. & St. Clair, C. C. An altered microbiome in urban coyotes mediates relationships between anthropogenic diet and poor health. *Sci. Rep.* **10**, 22207 (2020).
34. Widyanman, A. S. *et al.* Diversity of Oral Microbiome of Women From Urban and Rural Areas of Indonesia: A Pilot Study. *Front. Oral Health* **2**, (2021).
35. Djordjevic, S. P. *et al.* Genomic surveillance for antimicrobial resistance — a One Health perspective. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* **25**, 142–157 (2024).
36. Struelens, M. J. *et al.* Real-time genomic surveillance for enhanced control of infectious diseases and antimicrobial resistance. *Front. Sci.* **2**, (2024).
37. Afshinnekoo, E. *et al.* COVID-19 drug practices risk antimicrobial resistance evolution. *Lancet Microbe* **2**, e135–e136 (2021).

38. Danko, D. *et al.* A global metagenomic map of urban microbiomes and antimicrobial resistance. *Cell* **184**, 3376-3393.e17 (2021).
39. Stewart, J. D., Kremer, P., Shakya, K. M., Conway, M. & Saad, A. Outdoor Atmospheric Microbial Diversity Is Associated With Urban Landscape Structure and Differs From Indoor-Transit Systems as Revealed by Mobile Monitoring and Three-Dimensional Spatial Analysis. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **9**, (2021).
40. Peimbert, M. & Alcaraz, L. D. Where environmental microbiome meets its host: Subway and passenger microbiome relationships. *Mol. Ecol.* **32**, 2602–2618 (2023).
41. Ryan, F. J. Application of machine learning techniques for creating urban microbial fingerprints. *Biol. Direct* **14**, 13 (2019).
42. Chen, Y. *et al.* Environmental determinants and demographic influences on global urban microbiomes, antimicrobial resistance and pathogenicity. *Npj Biofilms Microbiomes* **9**, 94 (2023).
43. Johnson, M. T. J. & Munshi-South, J. Evolution of life in urban environments. *Science* **358**, eaam8327 (2017).
44. Wu, F. *et al.* SARS-CoV-2 Titers in Wastewater Are Higher than Expected from Clinically Confirmed Cases. *mSystems* **5**, 10.1128/msystems.00614-20 (2020).
45. Baldovin, T. *et al.* SARS-CoV-2 RNA detection and persistence in wastewater samples: An experimental network for COVID-19 environmental surveillance in Padua, Veneto Region (NE Italy). *Sci. Total Environ.* **760**, 143329 (2021).
46. D'Aoust, P. M. *et al.* Quantitative analysis of SARS-CoV-2 RNA from wastewater solids in communities with low COVID-19 incidence and prevalence. *Water Res.* **188**, 116560 (2021).
47. Peccia, J. *et al.* Measurement of SARS-CoV-2 RNA in wastewater tracks community infection dynamics. *Nat. Biotechnol.* **38**, 1164–1167 (2020).
48. Ahmed, W. *et al.* SARS-CoV-2 RNA monitoring in wastewater as a potential early warning system for COVID-19 transmission in the community: A temporal case study. *Sci. Total Environ.* **761**, 144216 (2021).
49. Gilbert, J. A. & Hartmann, E. M. The indoors microbiome and human health. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* **22**, 742–755 (2024).

50. Bosch, T. C. G. *et al.* The potential importance of the built-environment microbiome and its impact on human health. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **121**, e2313971121 (2024).
51. Fallet, M. *et al.* Early life microbial exposures shape the *Crassostrea gigas* immune system for lifelong and intergenerational disease protection. *Microbiome* **10**, 85 (2022).
52. Liu, Y. *et al.* Characterization of microbial communities in urban subway: connotation for indoor environment quality and public health. *Air Qual. Atmosphere Health* **17**, 1401–1413 (2024).
53. Bruno, A., Fumagalli, S., Ghisleni, G. & Labra, M. The Microbiome of the Built Environment: The Nexus for Urban Regeneration for the Cities of Tomorrow. *Microorganisms* **10**, 2311 (2022).
54. Flies, E. J., Jones, P., Buettel, J. C. & Brook, B. W. Compromised Ecosystem Services From Urban Aerial Microbiomes: A Review of Impacts on Human Immune Function. *Front. Ecol. Evol.* **8**, (2020).
55. Matthews, K., Cavagnaro, T., Weinstein, P. & Stanhope, J. Health by design; optimising our urban environmental microbiomes for human health. *Environ. Res.* **257**, 119226 (2024).
56. Vemuri, R. & Herath, M. P. Beyond the Gut, Emerging Microbiome Areas of Research: A Focus on Early-Life Microbial Colonization. *Microorganisms* **11**, 239 (2023).
57. Robinson, J. M. *et al.* Microbiome-Inspired Green Infrastructure: a bioscience roadmap for urban ecosystem health. *Arq Archit. Res. Q.* **25**, 292–303 (2021).
58. Fresia, P. *et al.* Urban metagenomics uncover antibiotic resistance reservoirs in coastal beach and sewage waters. *Microbiome* **7**, 35 (2019).
59. Dalton, K. R., Rock, C., Carroll, K. C. & Davis, M. F. One Health in hospitals: how understanding the dynamics of people, animals, and the hospital built-environment can be used to better inform interventions for antimicrobial-resistant gram-positive infections. *Antimicrob. Resist. Infect. Control* **9**, 78 (2020).
60. Afshinnekoo, E. *et al.* Precision Metagenomics: Rapid Metagenomic Analyses for Infectious Disease Diagnostics and Public Health Surveillance. *J. Biomol. Tech. JBT* **28**, 40–45 (2017).
61. O'Doherty, K. C., Virani, A. & Wilcox, E. S. The Human Microbiome and Public Health: Social and Ethical Considerations. *Am. J. Public Health* **106**, 414–420 (2016).
62. Amato, K. R. *et al.* The human gut microbiome and health inequities. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* **118**, e2017947118 (2021).

63. Hrudef, S. E. & Conant, B. The devil is in the details: emerging insights on the relevance of wastewater surveillance for SARS-CoV-2 to public health. *J. Water Health* **20**, 246–270 (2022).
64. Xu, X. *et al.* Wastewater genomic sequencing for SARS-CoV-2 variants surveillance in wastewater-based epidemiology applications. *Water Res.* **244**, 120444 (2023).
65. Karthikeyan, S. *et al.* Wastewater sequencing reveals early cryptic SARS-CoV-2 variant transmission. *Nature* **609**, 101–108 (2022).
66. Han, M. *et al.* Agricultural Risk Factors Influence Microbial Ecology in Honghu Lake. *Genomics Proteomics Bioinformatics* **17**, 76–90 (2019).
67. Prescott, S. L. Early-life environmental determinants of allergic diseases and the wider pandemic of inflammatory noncommunicable diseases. *J. Allergy Clin. Immunol.* **131**, 23–30 (2013).
68. Kaplan, R. C. *et al.* Gut microbiome composition in the Hispanic Community Health Study/Study of Latinos is shaped by geographic relocation, environmental factors, and obesity. *Genome Biol.* **20**, 219 (2019).
69. Astudillo-García, C., Hermans, S. M., Stevenson, B., Buckley, H. L. & Lear, G. Microbial assemblages and bioindicators as proxies for ecosystem health status: potential and limitations. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* **103**, 6407–6421 (2019).
70. Stewart, J. R. *et al.* The coastal environment and human health: microbial indicators, pathogens, sentinels and reservoirs. *Environ. Health* **7**, S3 (2008).
71. Qin, H., Sanders, C., Prasetyo, Y., Syukron, Muh. & Prentice, E. Exploring the dynamic relationships between risk perception and behavior in response to the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak. *Soc. Sci. Med.* **285**, 114267 (2021).

Figures

Figure 1. Contributing factors to the urban microbiome. Conceptual schematic illustrating interacting microbial domains across city environments. The urban microbiome spans atmospheric, vegetative, built, human, soil, engineered water, and hydrological systems, connected through microbial exchange via aerosols, runoff, and contact. Green infrastructure and vegetation serve as buffers linking the air, soil, and human layers, while urban fauna act as mobile microbial vectors across environments. River-coastal interface highlights hydrological feedbacks between wastewater and coastal systems. Together, these strata form a dynamic, multi-scale microbial network shaping the health and resilience of cities.

Urban Microbiome Roadmap

Figure 2. Roadmap for the future of microbially-informed cities. This conceptual roadmap outlines a trajectory for advancing urban metagenomics from descriptive mapping to a predictive practice. In the near term, standardized sampling and reference datasets will establish microbial and antimicrobial-resistance baselines across air, soil, wastewater, and built environments. Mid-term efforts will integrate environmental and clinical data, develop real-time microbial dashboards, and foster collaboration among public-health, engineering, and urban-planning sectors. Long-term goals emphasize the need for predictive modeling of microbial dynamics and ecological frameworks, culminating in globally connected networks that embed microbial literacy into urban health and sustainability policy.

Figure 3. The number of PubMed publications with the word “Microbiome” in the title or abstract over the past year, per country (top), normalized by the population size (bottom). The global picture of the urban microbiome is dominated by a handful of cities located in North America, Europe and East Asia. Rapidly urbanizing regions in Africa, South Asia and Latin America, where microbial dynamics may differ dramatically remain critically undersampled.

Table 1. Specific domains of current urban microbiome research, their clinical relevance and the comparative utility of emerging genomic technologies. This table synthesizes major research domains within urban microbiome science and maps each domain to its potential clinical and public health relevance, alongside the strengths and limitations of commonly used and emerging genomic technologies.

Domain	Representative Microbial Indicators	Emerging technology	Clinical / Public-Health Relevance
Wastewater Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viral RNA (SARS-CoV-2, influenza, enteric viruses). • AMR gene abundance (e.g., ESBLs, carbapenemases). • Pathogen load shifts (GI/respiratory agents) • Community-level “stress” signals (toxins, antimicrobial usage proxies). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ddPCR/qPCR gives fast, sensitive quantification for routine trending. • Metatranscriptomics helps distinguish active infections/signals (RNA activity) from relic DNA. • Shotgun metagenomics provides broad, unbiased detection + resistome profiling. • Hi-C links AMR genes to their host genomes (who carries what), improving actionability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early outbreak detection and variant tracking. • AMR trend forecasting at population scale. • Situational awareness for public-health response (surges, hotspots).
Built Environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air/surface microbiota composition (HVAC, wards, ICUs). • Opportunistic pathogens (MRSA, Acinetobacter, Pseudomonas). • Mobile resistome in high-touch areas. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shotgun metagenomics provides comprehensive profiling and relative abundance shifts across spaces/time. • Long-reads resolve plasmids/transposons → distinguish mobile AMR vs chromosomal, and support better assemblies. • Isolate WGS supports outbreak investigations (strain relatedness) and links environmental strains to clinical ones. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infection-control benchmarking (before/after interventions). • Transmission pathway mapping (room → device → patient risk). • Early warning for persistence of high-risk clones.
Transit & Public Spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air + surface microbial diversity. • Human–environment exchange taxa (skin/oral/respiratory signatures). • Seasonal/event-driven shifts (crowding, commuting patterns). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amplicons enable low-cost, high-throughput mapping of diversity across many sites and timepoints. • Shotgun metagenomics enables species/strain and functional profiling (including AMR). • Portable sequencing supports faster turnaround for targeted deployments (events, suspected clusters). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure quantification and risk modeling for respiratory/GI infections. • Public-health surveillance augmentation in high-density hubs.
Green & Soil Environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil/plant-associated diversity (Actinobacteria, mycorrhizal fungi). • Phyllosphere microbiome signatures. • Biodiversity indicators tied to urban ecology and human exposure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Metabarcoding tracks biodiversity at scale (who is there) across green corridors and seasons. • Shotgun metagenomics adds functional potential (nutrient cycling, allergen/virulence genes, resistome). • Metatranscriptomics highlights active functions under changing conditions (drought, pollution). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immune training / allergy modulation hypotheses (exposure ecology). • Environmental restoration monitoring and evaluation • Urban-planning evidence for “microbiome-positive” design.
Climate & Extreme Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-flood and post-heatwave community shifts. • Waterborne pathogen signals (e.g., Vibrio, enteric bacteria/viruses). • Bloom-associated microbes and toxin-related taxa. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-series metagenomics captures how communities reorganize after shocks and identifies emergent risks. • Metatranscriptomics indicates which pathogens/functions are active during/after events (not just present). • MST qPCR/ddPCR rapidly distinguishes contamination sources (human vs animal vs environmental) for response targeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Predict respiratory/waterborne disease patterns under climate stress. • Disaster-response decision support (boil-water advisories, cleanup prioritization).